

The impact of an online game-based financial education course: Multi-country experimental evidence

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Summary

1. The study examines the effectiveness of a game-based online financial education course in improving financial literacy across four countries: Belgium, Estonia, Italy, and Slovakia.
2. The intervention, called the *Financial Escape Room*, involves an interactive online game that teaches financial concepts like saving, budgeting, and interest calculation.
3. Game-based financial education significantly improved financial literacy in all participating countries, despite varying levels of baseline knowledge.
4. Policymakers are encouraged to integrate game-based learning into national financial education strategies, particularly targeting younger audiences.

1. Introduction

Financial literacy is increasingly recognized as a critical skill for individuals navigating complex financial systems (Remund, 2010). In recent years, the importance of equipping

citizens with the necessary financial knowledge and skills has grown due to the increasing complexity of financial products and services. Despite its importance, financial literacy remains low worldwide (De Beckker

et al., 2019), especially among young people (OECD, 2014, 2017, 2020).

In response to this issue, financial education has emerged as a natural solution that can be effectively implemented through deliberate efforts by policymakers. Some countries have already made financial education a mandatory part of their school curriculum, while others are considering it (OECD, 2022). However, beyond organizing engaging activities, it is crucial to assess whether these initiatives effectively enhance participants' skills (Kaiser & Menkhoff, 2017, 2020; Kaiser et al., 2022) using robust evaluation methodologies.

This policy brief summarizes key findings from a study by Cannistrà et al. (2024) evaluating the effectiveness of an online financial education course, conducted through a Randomized Controlled Trial (RCT) with 2,200 students across Belgium, Estonia, Italy, and Slovakia. It also discusses the implications for policymakers and school administrators, seeking to improve financial education using innovative approaches.

2. Theory and methods

When designing interventions in the field of financial education, it is important to consider recent trends in teaching methods and evaluation practices. Increasingly, educators are focusing on gamification, based on the idea that incorporating play-based learning elements can boost student engagement and motivation (Dicheva et al., 2015). Due to its practical relevance, the use of innovative learning-by-playing strategies in financial education is seen as a promising way to teach financial concepts (Batty et al., 2020). However, the current evidence supporting its effectiveness remains limited (Angel, 2018;

French et al., 2020; Kalmi & Rahko, 2022; Rodriguez-Raga & Martinez-Camelo, 2022; Sconti, 2022).

To address this gap in the literature, our study examines the effectiveness of a game-based activity, specifically a *Financial Escape Room*, in improving the financial literacy of secondary school students. The intervention consists of a simple and focused online game that covers key financial literacy topics such as calculating interest and percentage changes, managing bank accounts, and saving. In the game, players assume the role of a robber who must solve a series of financial challenges to unlock a bank vault.

We use a Randomized Controlled Trial (RCT) with 2,220 students to rigorously assess the impact of the *Financial Escape Room*. Randomization was carried out at the school level, with students being assigned to either the control or treatment group. A notable and unique feature of this study is the participation of students from four different countries: Belgium, Estonia, Italy, and Slovakia. Previous research has indicated that the effectiveness of financial literacy interventions may vary, as cultural factors can influence financial literacy outcomes beyond individual socio-economic backgrounds (De Beckker et al., 2020). Our study sheds light on the external validity of findings, i.e. can we transfer findings from one context to other contexts?

3. Results

The study by Cannistrà et al. (2024) provides robust evidence that game-based financial education can significantly improve financial literacy. Participants in the online course demonstrate improved understanding of financial concepts as compared to control groups. The interactive nature of the game,

which required participants to make financial decisions in a simulated environment, helped reinforce learning and improve retention of financial knowledge.

The research, conducted across multiple countries with diverse economic backgrounds, confirms the broad applicability of game-based learning in financial education. Despite varying levels of pre-existing financial literacy, participants from all countries showed significant improvement, suggesting that this approach can be universally effective.

4. Policy implications

Given the findings, several key policy recommendations can be drawn:

1. Incorporating Game-Based Learning into Financial Education Programs

Policymakers and teachers should consider integrating game-based learning into national financial education strategies. The evidence suggests that this approach is not only effective but also scalable and adaptable to different cultural and economic contexts. Governments and educational institutions could collaborate with developers to create tailored financial education games that address specific national or regional financial literacy gaps.

2. Targeting Younger Audiences

The interactive nature of game-based learning makes it particularly well-suited for younger audiences, who are often difficult to engage through traditional financial education methods. Moreover, the game-based learning allows for adaptive learning and tailored feedback, and hence accommodating to the heterogeneity in classrooms. Policymakers should prioritize the development and dissemination of such programs in schools, ensuring that financial education is both

accessible and appealing to the next generation.

3. Leveraging Technology for Wider Reach

The online delivery of the game-based course is a key factor in its success, offering accessibility to a broad audience at a low cost. Policymakers should invest in digital infrastructure and online platforms that facilitate the widespread adoption of such educational tools. This is especially important in regions where access to traditional financial education resources is limited.

4. Monitoring and Evaluation

While the initial results are promising, continuous monitoring and evaluation of game-based financial education programs are essential to ensure their long-term effectiveness. Policymakers should establish mechanisms for tracking the impact of these programs over time, including follow-up studies to assess knowledge retention and behavioral changes. To facilitate long-term impact evaluation administrative micro-data should be made more open for researchers, and administrative data sources should be better mutually connected.

5. Conclusions

The study on the impact of an online game-based financial education course provides compelling evidence that innovative, interactive approaches can significantly enhance financial literacy across different countries and demographic groups. For policymakers, this presents an opportunity to rethink traditional financial education strategies and embrace methods that are more engaging, accessible, and effective. By incorporating game-based learning into financial education policies, governments can better equip their citizens with the knowledge

and skills needed to make informed financial decisions, ultimately contributing to more financially secure and resilient societies.

Further research is needed to explore the long-term effects of game-based financial education and its impact on actual financial behaviors. Additionally, studies should investigate how different demographic groups respond to such interventions to tailor programs more effectively. Finally, understanding the cost-effectiveness of these programs will be crucial for policymakers aiming to implement them on a large scale.

What is EFFeCt ?

EFFeCt is an impact-driven research project aiming to enhance the quality of education in the EU by providing evidence-based policy recommendations and conducting rigorous research on the education policies of individual EU member states.

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Further Information:

Cannistrà, M., De Beckker, K., Agasisti, T., Amagir, A., Pöder, K., Vartiak, L., De Witte, K. (2024). The impact of an online game-based financial education course: Multi-country experimental evidence. *Journal of Comparative Economics*. In Press. DOI: 10.1016/j.jce.2024.08.001.

You can experience the Financial Education Escape Room yourself by accessing it through this link:
https://toll-net.be/moodle/xertetoolkits/play.php?template_id=40885#page1

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